

A piezoelectric, single-actuator fretting-fatigue rig based on three-point bending

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Abstract

Fretting fatigue test programmes often require tight control of multiple load components at a contact (bulk stress in the specimen, normal load, tangential load and, in some geometries, a contact moment). State-of-the-art laboratory rigs commonly achieve this using multiple servo-hydraulic actuators and long load paths, which increase cost, noise and maintenance burden, and can introduce inter-channel coupling and control-fidelity issues that become more severe at higher cycling frequencies. This paper proposes a compact alternative rig concept in which all required load components are generated synchronously by a single piezoelectric actuator acting on a short, stiff three-point-bending specimen. This bending provides the cyclic bulk stress while a compliant, stiffness-tuned pad fixture provides the required contact normal load; an inclined reaction path superposes a controlled tangential load with a prescribed shear/normal ratio. The concept removes the need for hydraulic infrastructure and for specimens with tangs, enabling lower-cost specimens, fewer grip/tang failures, and the potential for substantially higher test frequencies within the force/displacement envelope relevant to fretting fatigue.

Keywords: fretting fatigue; piezoelectric actuator; three-point bending; load path; multiaxial fatigue; test rig design

Highlights

- Proposes a compact fretting-fatigue rig driven by a single piezoelectric actuator.
- Generates bulk stress, normal load and tangential load synchronously via structural design (no channel synchronisation).
- Replaces axial dog-bone specimens (with tangs) with a low-cost beam specimen in three-point bending.
- Reduces hydraulic infrastructure, noise, maintenance and risk of leaks/oil hazards.
- Enables higher cycling frequencies and larger design-of-experiments matrices through reduced test time and specimen cost.

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Nomenclature

σ_b	bulk stress parallel to the contact surface (in the specimen)
P	contact normal load
Q	contact tangential (shear) load
M	resultant moment transmitted across the contact (where relevant)
μ	coefficient of friction
L	span between outer supports of the three-point-bending specimen
F	central point load applied to the beam (from the actuator)
δ	mid-span deflection of the beam
E	Young's modulus
I	second moment of area of the beam cross-section

1 Introduction

Fretting fatigue describes accelerated crack nucleation and early crack growth driven by cyclic loading, often resulting in small-amplitude relative motion and a fluctuating bulk stress. It is a critical durability issue in many assemblies (e.g., dovetail roots, splines, bolted or clamped joints) and remains challenging to predict because stresses are multiaxial and highly gradient-dominated near the contact edge. Standard treatments characterise the combination of bulk stress and frictional contact tractions, including whether the interface operates in stick/partial-slip or gross-slip regimes (often summarised via fretting maps). Experimental data therefore remain essential for validating mechanics-based models and for ranking materials, surface treatments and contact geometries under representative loading paths. [1, 2, 3]

Laboratory fretting-fatigue rigs typically attempt to reproduce, in simplified two-dimensional representation, up to four load components acting at the contact: (i) cyclic bulk stress in the specimen, (ii) contact normal load P , (iii) contact shear load Q , and (iv) a contact moment M for geometries such as flat-and-rounded (“flat and radiused”) pads. Recent studies have emphasised that fretting-fatigue life and crack-driving fields can depend on the load path and phase relationships between these components, and that unintended moment coupling within an apparatus can bias the intended boundary conditions. [1, 4, 5]

2 Background: multi-channel servo-hydraulic fretting-fatigue rigs

2.1 Load components and their experimental control

In the plane-strain idealisation commonly used for pad-on-specimen fretting tests, the contact state may be represented by P , Q and (where present) M , together with the remote/bulk stress σ_b in the specimen. Many laboratory rigs control σ_b and Q by applying differential axial loads at the specimen ends, while a third actuator applies P . Where the geometry and load introduction produce a moment across the contact, either an additional degree of freedom is required or an equivalent representation must be adopted when interpreting the near-edge fields relevant to crack nucleation. [1, 2, 5, 6]

2.2 Practical limitations of multi-actuator hydraulic rigs

Servo-hydraulic actuators are versatile and can deliver large forces over long strokes, which is advantageous for many structural fatigue tests. However, for fretting-fatigue studies requiring tight proportional control of several loads, bespoke multi-channel rigs introduce several recurring problems: (i) high capital and running cost (pump sets, plumbing, servo-valves), (ii) noise and maintenance burden, (iii) risks associated with leaks or burst hoses, and (iv) control-fidelity limitations arising from electrical noise, repeatability and coupling between channels and through the specimen/fixture compliance.

These limitations become more acute as the requested cycling frequency increases. Asymmetric stiffness in the load paths, large structural elements and long hydraulic lines can place low-frequency modes within the operating range, and multi-channel synchronisation must remain accurate cycle-to-cycle to preserve a desired partial-slip state at the contact.

2.3 Error accumulation and loss of partial-slip condition

A particular concern is the accumulation of errors across independent channels. Consider a common configuration in which bulk loading is applied by two opposed actuators: their mean provides the bulk stress, while their difference provides the shear force at the contact. If, in a given cycle, one bulk actuator and the normal actuator underachieve while the second bulk actuator overachieves, the resulting increase in Q combined with a reduction in P can raise the traction ratio Q/P . Under load-controlled operation, tests are typically designed to remain in partial slip; if the erroneous traction ratio exceeds the effective friction coefficient μ , gross sliding can occur and the pad may translate along the specimen, invalidating the test and damaging the contact.

2.4 Programme size, specimen cost and non-gauge failures

Industrial fretting-fatigue problems are often associated with nominally stuck contacts excited by vibration; representative excitation frequencies can be in the hundreds of hertz, and the relevant lives may be 10^7 – 10^9 cycles. Running such programmes on hydraulic rigs at the required loads may therefore take weeks or months per test, which constrains experimental matrices and reduces the number of repeats that can be afforded. In addition, axial dog-bone specimens with tangs are prone to fretting and premature failures in the grips/tangs, particularly when large clamping loads are required. [1, 2]

Consequently, datasets in the published fretting-fatigue literature are frequently sparse, with limited repeats and little scope for full design-of-experiments (DOE) matrices. [1]

3 Proposed concept: single-actuator piezoelectric rig using three-point bending

3.1 Concept overview and expected advantages

The proposed rig replaces hydraulic actuation entirely with a piezoelectric actuator and replaces the axial dog-bone specimen with a short beam specimen in three-point bending. The core idea is to use a stiffness-dominated structural arrangement so that a single actuator displacement simultaneously establishes: (i) a target bulk stress range in the tensile surface of the beam, (ii) a target normal load P through a compliance-tuned pad support, and (iii) a target tangential load Q by introducing the pad reaction at a prescribed angle. Because all loads derive from one imposed force, inter-channel synchronisation is eliminated.

Piezoelectric actuators can provide high force over small strokes, and have been widely used in high-frequency fatigue testing. [7, 8] When combined with short, stiff load paths, this makes

them attractive for accelerating fretting fatigue programmes, or enabling tests to the giga-cycle range.

Specimen cost and lead time should be considered when specifying a fretting-fatigue test programme. Such programmes are often initiated following an unexpected in-service failure, so delays associated with material procurement and complex and precise machining can be as limiting as the test duration. Figure 1 illustrates the material waste and manufacturing complexity associated with conventional axial specimens. By contrast, a three-point-bending specimen can be manufactured accurately at a fraction of the cost: when machined from suitable square stock, preparation typically requires only cutting to length, milling to size and applying the required surface finish, with minimal material waste.

Figure 1: Examples of specimen designs used in previous fretting-fatigue test programmes (to scale). The proposed three-point-bending specimen is shown on the right.

3.2 Specimen and contact configuration

A square-section (or rectangular) beam is simply supported at two outer points. The actuator applies a central point load F , producing a maximum bending moment at mid-span. The lower specimen surface above the loading nose experiences cyclic compression, while the upper surface experiences cyclic tension. A secondary fretting contact may occur at the central loading point on the compressive surface; under the intended loading this location is not expected to be crack-driving, but it should be protected or monitored during testing. The primary fretting-fatigue contact of interest is placed opposite the central loading point on the upper, tensile specimen surface, using a pad with the desired geometry and material. The beam deflects into the fretting pad to generate the contact normal load P .

3.3 Generating bulk stress in three-point bending

For a simply supported beam with span L and a central point load F , the maximum bending stress at the outer fibre is

$$\sigma_{b,\max} = \frac{3FL}{2bh^2} \quad (1)$$

Figure 2: Schematic (not to scale) of the proposed rig architecture. The blue region denotes the stiff supporting frame.

for a rectangular section (width b , height h). If the actuator is operated in displacement control, the mid-span deflection δ is related to F by

$$\delta = \frac{FL^3}{48EI}. \quad (2)$$

Combining these gives

$$\sigma_{b,\max} = \frac{6Eh\delta}{L^2} \quad (3)$$

for a rectangular section (using $I = bh^3/12$). This highlights why a specimen with a small length and large height is advantageous for piezo actuation: high cyclic bulk stress can be obtained from small δ because the specimen is stiff.

This simple three-point-bending arrangement can be augmented to increase the effective stiffness seen by the actuator without increasing specimen complexity at the fretting contact. One option is to attach the beam to a stiffening web or back-plate so that the neutral axis is shifted away from the fretting surface (analogous to a T-section). This reduces the actuator stroke required to achieve a given surface stress, at the expense of a higher force requirement. Figure 3 illustrates a configuration in which the fretting specimen is clamped to a separate stiffening web, preserving simple specimen manufacture while providing additional stiffness. In this case the bulk stress arises from a combination of bending and axial loading. The dimensions must be considered such that the required clamping forces at the ends do not cause fretting fatigue failures at the clamping positions.

3.4 Generating normal and tangential contact loads with one actuator

The pad opposite the central loading point is backed by a fixture of specified compliance (e.g., flexure, spring stack, or calibrated elastic element). As the beam deflects, it is driven into the pad, generating the normal load P . By choosing the fixture stiffness and preload, the mean and amplitude of P can be selected.

To superpose a shear load Q without adding an actuator, the reaction force from the pad support can be applied at an angle θ to the specimen surface (i.e., non-orthogonal to the local normal). This gives $Q/P = \tan \theta$, enabling the shear/normal ratio to be set geometrically. In

Figure 3: Schematic of a beam-stiffening sub-assembly for use with piezoelectric actuators. The original three-point-bending specimen (blue) is clamped to the ends of the stiffening web (green). The assembly is loaded in three-point bending between the red pins.

practice, flexural compliance and friction in secondary interfaces must be managed so that θ and the effective load ratio remain stable over the operating load history.

3.5 The contact moment and flat-and-rounded pad geometries

Flat-and-rounded pad geometries, common in blade/disc attachments, may transmit a resultant moment M across the contact. In many test rigs, M is not independently controllable and may arise from the way the shear load is introduced and reacted. Recent analyses have shown how moment coupling can be measured and how equivalent load representations can be used to account for the influence of M when matching the near-edge fields. More generally, contact edge geometry (including edge rounding) alters the local pressure distribution and the near-edge asymptotes under combined normal and tangential loading, and should therefore be carefully controlled and documented in fretting-fatigue testing. [2, 5, 9, 10]

3.6 Implications for test fidelity and achievable frequency

Because all loads are generated synchronously from one actuator displacement, the principal error mechanism described in Section 2.3 (cycle-to-cycle accumulation of independent channel errors) is removed. In practice, this relaxes the constraint that cycling frequency must be reduced to maintain multi-channel fidelity. The short, stiff load paths of the proposed rig also increase structural resonance frequencies, expanding the usable frequency range. Taken together, these features suggest the potential for substantially higher test frequencies than multi-actuator hydraulic rigs for comparable load control fidelity, though the achievable improvement factor will depend on the final design and instrumentation.

4 Conclusions

A compact, piezoelectric, single actuator fretting fatigue rig concept has been proposed. By placing the specimen in three-point bending and engineering the pad support compliance and reaction angle, the bulk stress, normal load and tangential load can be generated synchronously from one actuator displacement, removing multi-channel synchronisation challenges that limit the frequency and fidelity of conventional hydraulic rigs. Replacing tanged dog-bone specimens with a beam specimen reduces unintentional specimen failures and specimen cost, enabling larger, better-replicated experimental matrices. The next steps are detailed mechanical design, dynamic characterisation, and validation testing against benchmark conditions from established rigs.

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